

THE IMPORTANCE OF PAREMAS IN EXPRESSING INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION

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Annotation. The article analyzes the axiological component of verbal units that form paremiological funds in languages with different structures. Phrases, proverbs, and sayings reflect national and cultural characteristics and values accepted in a certain ethnic community. The author's understanding of the axiological component is presented, which is interpreted as a value associated with the assessment, present in the semantics of a paremiological unit.

Keywords: paremia, proverb, value, evaluation, axiological component, intercultural communication, phraseological unit.

Proverbs, sayings, and non-authorial sayings are classified in this article as paremias or units of the paremiological fund. We believe that the use of "paremiologeme" (like "phraseologeme") is also possible as a synonym. The study of units of the paremiological fund involves the use of such concepts as: culture, values, language, consciousness, and communication. The uniqueness of paremias lies in the fact that they are analyzed by scientists working in various fields - linguistics, cultural studies, axiology, psycholinguistics, philosophy, and communication theory. A paremia is a message that can be included in an act of (intercultural) communication. The semantic component of a paremia manifests itself in determining the value of an object or phenomenon concerning other objects or phenomena. It can reflect the results of the action of categorization or classification mechanisms. The didactics of paremias can be expressed in explicit and implicit forms, but, in one way or another, it is present in each verbal unit. The value component is one of the serious obstacles to successful communication, so a projection analysis of the functioning of paremias with a dominant axiological component in the context of intercultural communication was carried out.

Proverbs (as well as phraseological units) are exceptionally fertile material for studying national and cultural specificity. According to V.N. Telia, these linguistic units are connected "...with the material, social or spiritual culture of a linguistic community and can testify to its cultural and national experience and traditions." The representativeness of cultural codes is highest in the semantics of linguistic units that form the paremiological fund of the language, which is confirmed by the results of studies by Russian philologists. Both proverbs and phraseological units testify to the national cultural specificity of linguistic

consciousness. These are linguistic units that objectify the cultural specificity of the images of consciousness of a certain ethnolinguocultural community. Semiotically coded results of linguistic activity of representatives of a certain linguoculture are cultural heritage. Acquaintance with them affects the formation of linguistic consciousness of individuals and the community as a whole. "The content of internal images of consciousness, reflecting objective reality in the form of subjective ideal reality, constitutes knowledge about cultural objects (that have fallen into the field of perception), which can be formed in two ways: firstly, by analyzing internal images, i.e. by analyzing subjective, ideal reality, if it is externalized (objectified), and secondly, by analyzing the cultural objects themselves, i.e. by analyzing objective reality"[2]

The semantic component of a paremia manifests itself when determining the value of an object or phenomenon concerning other objects or phenomena. The axiological component can reflect the results of the action of categorization or classification mechanisms. Finally, the axiological component of paremias can be presented in prescriptions of a certain focus that have a didactic content. Modern humanitarization of knowledge stimulates the search for points of contact in philosophical views and interpretations of linguistic phenomena. An appeal to the origins of axiology within the framework of this linguistic study is dictated by the need for an interdisciplinary nature of the object under study. This is exactly the case when "... within the framework of each scientific approach, it becomes increasingly difficult to keep the object of your research in front of you and increasingly difficult to identify the mechanisms of its objectification".

The axiological component in proverbs or sayings can be represented in the form of comments on a specific value (material or immaterial), which in the terminology of G. Rickert are called "goods". Proverbs also offer an assessment of goods - real or actual objects associated with value. A significant part of proverbs sounds like edification, and instruction, which is a recommendation for achieving a behavioral model. Some proverbs and sayings are a declaration of values of moral life. Proverbs and sayings included in the subject assessment group describe the actor: *Ex ungue leonem* (You can recognize a lion by his claws. You can tell a bird by its flight). Traits that appear positive or negative in the axiological "coordinate system" of a particular society are emphasized: Handsome in appearance, but worthless in soul; The grave will correct a hunchback. As a rule, in such paremias, the subject is characterized through his behavior or actions: The brave will find where the timid will lose; The happy will

neither burn in fire nor drown in fire. Evidence of the subject's assessment is some fact or action: To teach a scholar is to spoil, and to teach a fool is like curing a dead man; C'est son fort; il est ferré sur cette matière (He's an expert on this); La garde meurt mais ne se rend pas (The guard dies, but never surrenders). Note the universality of the semantic structure, "the one who...", "the one who...". For example, the Latin structure qui est is presented in the proverb Dives est, qui sapiens est (Rich is he who is wise), and this model has retained its relevance to this day in Russian, English, and French. The didactics of these proverbs are expressed explicitly in most cases. Paremiias can be classified from the standpoint of different approaches. The system-structural approach analyzes the connections between components within paremiias. The cognitive approach emphasizes conceptual content, since paremiias are unique linguistic units whose cognitive structures contain complex conglomerates of primary and secondary conceptual knowledge. The knowledge recorded in sayings and proverbs explicates the peculiarities of an ethnic community's understanding of the surrounding world. Considering paremiias in a pragmalinguistic and cognitive-discursive focus also sheds light on their differences from other linguistic units. The organization of the conceptual space of paremiias is considered using such concepts of cognitive science as "frame" and "scenario". Finally, paremiias are studied based on the provisions of the theory of speech activity and the theory of linguistic consciousness, since paremiias accumulate a worldview through the combined organization of a system of images. The study of paremiias is a popular topic in linguistics and cultural studies. But despite the significant number of works, it cannot be said that all aspects of this phenomenon have been covered exhaustively to date.

Conclusion. An interdisciplinary approach to the study of the axiological component of paremiological units and the features of its manifestation in intercultural communication is described. An understanding of the axiological component as a special meaning in the semantics of paremiias associated with value or assessment, as well as with the process of categorization is presented. Based on G. Rickert's interpretation of such phenomena as "value" and "assessment", we proposed to classify all paremiias containing an axiological component into five groups: behavioral instructions, object assessment, subject assessment, subject behavior assessment, and declarations of life values. It was proven that assessment can be presented both in the form of direct explicit didactics and didactics with inferential knowledge. On the one hand, this approach demonstrated the effectiveness of distinguishing proverbs based on

the specific content of the assessment, and on the other hand, it made it possible to identify areas of semantic inconsistencies that actualize “interference” in the process of intercultural communication.

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